

CONCEPT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SHARIA MICRO-FINANCE INSTITUTIONS (ANALYSIS OF ADINUGRAHA THINKING CONTRIBUTIONS)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7463541

Wahyudin Ali Ikhrom¹

Tamamudin²

ABSTRACT

Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha is a Lecturer at IAIN Pekalongan, he is also active in writing books, scientific journals with the theme of Islamic studies. This article intends to study and describe specifically about Adinugraha's thoughts on the concept and implementation of Islamic microfinance institutions. The approach used is a literature review whose primary source comes from his very interesting works on Islamic studies. The concept and implementation of Islamic financial institutions according to Adinugraha, Islamic microfinance institutions (LKMS) are the same form as MFIs in general, the difference is the Islamic principles applied to products, contracts and operations. LKMS serves financing needs and facilitates a financing system for all micro-sectors. In the practice of Islamic economics, both banks and LKMS must avoid Magrib, an acronym for masyir, gharar and usury. In its implementation, LKMs are more accessible to the public, both savings and loans because they are in accordance with the agreement of related parties without being burdened with using sharia principles.

Keywords: Sharia Principles, LKMS, Adinugraha's Thoughts

¹ Islamic Economics Undergraduate Student; State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan, Jawa Tengah, Indonesia. E-mail: wahyudinaliikhrom@mhs.iainpekalongan.ac.id

² Lecturer of Islamic Economics Department; State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan, Jawa Tengah, Indonesia. E-mail: tamamudin@iainpekalongan.ac.id

Preliminary

Islamic microfinance institutions have a clear market segment, namely the lower middle level community, so that LKMS activities will be centered in business centers at the micro and medium level communities such as traditional markets for small and medium businesses, as well as rural communities and urban peripheries. LKMS has characteristics that are close to the community and it is not uncommon for LKMS to try to come to the community (pick up the ball), this is what makes LKMS popular and close to the community. The emergence of Islamic microfinance institutions today shows a trend that is getting better in the midst of the global crisis that hit this country. Many of the products offered are quite varied so that customers can choose according to their needs (Rifki Muhammad, 2010).

Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) when referring to Law No.1 of 2013 concerning Microfinance Institutions are defined as financial institutions specifically established to provide business development services and community empowerment, either through loans or financing in micro-scale businesses to members and the community, savings management, as well as providing business development consulting services that are not solely for profit (Baskara, 2013).

The word "micro" in the mention of Sharia Microfinance Institutions gives a more meaning to indicate a smaller scope/coverage level. With the comparison assumption that one of the large financial institutions is in the form of a bank with large-scale capital, then a microfinance institution is another formation of a bank or the like that has a small capital and is intended for the micro and small business sector. In this sense, it is categorized into Baitul Mal Wattamwil, Sharia Cooperatives and Sharia People's Pre-credit Banks (BPRS).(Farid, 2018).

According to Adinugraha (2017) In the structure of Islamic financial institutions, they are grouped into Islamic commercial banks, Islamic rural banks and sharia cooperatives (Bait al-Māl wa at-Tamwil). These three institutions have different products and market shares. However, in terms of the principles and instruments used, the three Islamic financial institutions (LKS) do not have a fairly basic difference, only in the scope of their activities. Baitul Maal Wat Tamwil (BMT) as the name implies consists of two main functions, namely: Baitul Maal (house of treasure), receiving deposits of zakat, infaq, and alms and optimizing the distribution in accordance with the regulations and mandates. Meanwhile, Baitul Tamwil (house for property development), develops productive businesses and invests in improving the economic quality of micro and small entrepreneurs by, among other things, encouraging saving activities and supporting the financing of economic activities. Islamic microfinance

institutions, in this case BMT, have considerable development potential with the existence of community needs and strong development policy support. The purpose of writing this article is to find out and describe how the concept and implementation of Islamic microfinance institutions is based on Adinugraha's perspective.

Research methods

In this study, the type of research that the author conducts is research using a descriptive qualitative approach, namely the data collected in the form of words, not in the form of numbers. Descriptive research is a form of research that is shown to describe or describe existing phenomena, both natural phenomena and human engineering, because this research aims to clarify the state of the subject under study.

Qualitative research also has different philosophical assumptions, research strategies, and methods of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data. Although the process is the same, qualitative procedures still rely on data in the form of text and images, have unique steps in data analysis, and are sourced from different research strategies (John W . Creswell, 2010).

In this case, the author only analyzes Adinugraha's thoughts on the concept and implementation of sharia microfinance institutions. Then it is combined with library research by analyzing his works which are used as primary sources and other books as secondary data sources related to this research, literature and articles obtained from the website (Burhan Bungin, 2005).

The focus of this research is to find out how the concept and implementation of Islamic microfinance institutions (analysis of the contribution of Adinugraha's thoughts) can be said to be very worthy of study because it is very interesting so that it can add knowledge and insight about sharia microfinance institutions.

HASIL DAN PEMBAHASAN

Biografi Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha

Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha is a PNS Lecturer at IAIN Pekalongan (2019-present). The man who is usually called Hendri was born in Serang on March 11, 1987, he started his lecturer career since graduating from Master of Islamic Studies (Islamic Economics Concentration) UII Yogyakarta by becoming a Permanent Lecturer at UDINUS Semarang (2012-2019). His Doctoral Education (S3) took the concentration of Halal Management at UIN Walisongo Semarang (2017-2020). Apart from being a lecturer, he is also active in writing books, national and international scientific journals with the theme of Islamic economics and Islamic studies.

CURRICULUM VITAE

A. Self Identity

1. Name : Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha
2. Place & Date Born : Serang, 11 Maret 1987
3. Address : Jl. Srinindito Timur V, RT. 03/03, Ngemplak Simongan, Semarang Barat.
4. HP : 085659159132
5. Email : hendri.hermawan@iainpekalongan.ac.id

B. Educational History

1. Formal Education Background

- | Periode | Degree | Institution |
|---------------|---------------------------------------|---|
| • 2017 – 2020 | S3 Islamic Studies – Halal Management | Islamic State University Walisongo Semarang |
| • 2009 – 2012 | Master Majoring in Islamic Economic | Universitas Islam Indonesia Yogyakarta |
| • 2005 – 2009 | Bachelor Majoring in Islamic Economic | Universitas Islam Indonesia Yogyakarta |
| • 2001 – 2004 | Senior High School | Ponpes Modern Subulussalam Tangerang |
| • 1998 – 2001 | Junior High School | Ponpes Modern Subulussalam Tangerang |
| • 1992 – 1998 | Elementary School | SDN 1 Sukamanah Serang |

2. Nonformal Education Background

- 2005 – 2009 Pondok Pesantren Sunan Pandanaran Jogja Komplek 4 (Asrama Mahasiswa)

C. Academic Achievement

- 1) Recipients of the Indonesian Ministry of Religion 5000 Domestic Doctoral Scholarships in 2017.
- 2) The Best Participant of the Integrated Sharia Finance Training of Trainer, Financial Services Authority, 2018.
- 3) Recipients of Copyright (Copy Right) for Writings with the Title of Islamic Emoticons: Towards Branding of Halal Products (A Research Agenda), Based on Copyright Registration Letter No: EC00201806914, Ministry of Law and Human Rights, 2018

D. Work Experience

Year	Position / Field of Work
2013-2019	Permanent Lecturer at the Dian Nuswantoro University Foundation
2019-Now	IAIN Pekalongan PNS Lecture

E. Research and Published Articles

Year	Research Title
2018	Desa Wisata Halal: Konsep dan Implementasinya di Indonesia
2019	Perspective Review of Islamic Study Towards Qaryah Mubārakah's (The Blessed Village) Values in the Tourism Village
2020	Developing Model of Halal Food Purchase Intention among Indonesian Non-Muslim Consumers: An Explanatory Sequential Mixed Methods Research
2021	Halal Tourism in Indonesia: An Indonesian Council of Ulama National Sharia Board Fatwa Perspective

F. Published Books

Year	Book Title
• 2020	PERBANKAN SYARIAH: Fenomena Terkini dan Praktiknya di Indonesia
• 2021	HALAL LIFESTYLE: Theory and Practice in Indonesia

Adinugraha's works

Adinugraha besides serving as a lecturer, he also has a passion for writing scientific works such as writing articles, books, scientific journals both nationally and internationally with the theme of Islamic economics and Islamic studies. This can be seen from his writings which can add to the scientific treasures of readers, especially in the field of Islamic economics and Islamic studies. As a lecturer who is productive in writing scientific papers with his interesting ideas on Islamic economics and Islamic studies, especially related to the problems of Islamic microfinance institutions.

The articles related to this research include: 1) Application of the Rule of al-Ghunm bi al-Ghurm in Mushārah Financing in Islamic Banking Introduction The basic concept in Islamic banking is the concept of division. 2) Implementation of ijārah and imbt at the BRI Syariah Yogyakarta branch. 3) Sharia Marketing in Islamic Microfinance Institutions: Concept and Implementation in Puskopsyah DIY. 4) Fundraising Management Optimization of Zakat Infaq and Alms in The Countryside. And many more of his writings can be accessed at <https://scholar.google.co.id/citations?user=5jKlptMAAAAJ&hl=en>, .

The Contribution of Adinugraha's Thoughts on the Concept and Implementation of Islamic Microfinance Institutions

Adinugraha as a person who has a penchant for writing scientific works such as journal articles, books and other written works, especially on Islamic economics and Islamic studies on a national and international scale, is certainly one of his strengths.

The advantages in the field of writing have opened new horizons in the world of writing. Which can be very useful in adding to the repertoire of knowledge in the field of Islamic economics. The thoughts that Adinugraha has about Islamic microfinance institutions are based on his educational background from childhood to the present which is steeped in the study of Islamic economics.

The contribution of his good thoughts is certainly very interesting to study and analyze in increasing scientific knowledge. The contributions of Adinugraha's thoughts on the concept and implementation of Islamic microfinance include: 1) Utilization of Waqf in the Midst of the Covid-19 Pandemic in the Maqashid Al-Syariah Perspective 2) Implementation of Ijārah and Imbt at Bank Bri Syariah Yogyakarta Branch 3) Sharia

Marketing at Microfinance Institutions Islam: Concept and Implementation at Puskopsyah D.I. Yogyakarta.

Empowerment of Waqf in the Midst of the Covid-19 Pandemic In the Perspective of Maqashid Al-Syariah

According to Adinugraha, the use of waqf instruments to overcome social and economic problems should also be able to provide opportunities for handling the COVID-19 pandemic that is hitting the world at this time. Handling the pandemic requires strategic and clear goals, as stated in the maqashid sharia concept.

The COVID-19 pandemic that occurred in Indonesia had a fairly serious impact and caused a lot of unrest in the community. This is because people lost their income, where before this pandemic, people were able to carry out economic and business activities normally, but after the Covid-19, many restrictions were put in place by the government so that this caused the average income of the community to tend to decrease or not. any income received. Therefore, if it is allowed to continue, the economic condition in Indonesia will get worse and the poverty rate in Indonesia will be even higher. This is evidenced by BPS data (2021) that the percentage of poor people in Indonesia in semester 1 of 2019 was 9.41 percent, increasing to 10.19 percent in semester 2 of 2020. (Miftakhuddin et al., 2021).

Waqf in Arabic "Waqf" means "al-Habs", where a word in the form of masdar (infinitive noun) according to the subject in question, namely standing or stopping. If this understanding of stopping is connected with the science of recitation, it is a procedure for calling the letters, where and how to stop. So, in the sense of recitation, it means to stop reading. Then also waqf is interpreted to hold (something) with wealth (Siah, 2010).

Waqf is an instrument that has the potential to be developed by Muslims, especially for countries that are categorized as developing countries. In various countries, waqf has been widely used in productive terms, the management of this waqf should have been carried out from the start, so that within a certain time waqf can be used to empower people (K. Lubis, 2010).

Utilization of waqf is an activity to plan, implement and coordinate supervision in order to collect, distribute and utilize waqf. This activity has been regulated in Law Number 41 of 2004 concerning Waqf and is carried out by the Indonesian Waqf Board (Aziz, 2017). Menurut According to scholars, waqf funds are allowed to be managed for the benefit of the people. Then,

in its management, it is not the same as the management of zakat or shodaqoh in general. The waqf manager can maintain the waqf property as a whole, but strive to develop it so that it can provide good and optimal output to the mauquf alaih

Adinugraha believes that the government's policies to break the chain of transmission of COVID-19 can have a negative impact on the economy. The implementation of the PSBB policy has disrupted economic and business activities, especially in Indonesia. The role of waqf at this time to deal with the pandemic is considered not optimal, this is influenced by the lack of public understanding of the development of waqf in Indonesia so that they only know waqf of land and buildings. Nevertheless, the utilization of waqf has the potential to help overcome the problems of the COVID-19 pandemic, namely by providing assistance to hospitals and health facilities. Then, when viewed from the perspective of maqashid sharia, the utilization of waqf in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic is in accordance with the three concepts of needs described by Imam Syatibi, namely dharuriyah, hajiyah and tahsiniyah.

Implementation of Ijārah and Imbt at Bank Bri Syariah Yogyakarta Branch

According to Adinugraha, in essence, the main factor in the emergence of Islamic banking in the Islamic world is the spread of "interest". Where interest is legally categorized as usury and the law is haram, efforts have begun in a number of Muslim countries to establish alternative institutions to usury (conventional) banks.

As for *ijarah* in Islamic bank financing for the procurement of goods plus the agreed profit with a rental payment system without ending with ownership (Martono, 2002).

Meanwhile, *ijārah vomitīyah bi al-tamlīk* in sharia banking is a rental agreement between a bank (*muājir*) and a tenant (*mustajīr*) which is followed by a promise that at a certain time the ownership of the leased property will transfer to the *mustajīr*. Meanwhile, the rental price and selling price are agreed at the beginning of the agreement. This is in line with the words of Ibn Qudamah regarding *ijarah*, namely "wa kullu mā jāza tsamanan fī al-bay"i jāza iwad han fi al-*ijārah*."(Ij et al., n.d.)

Adinugraha assumes that the implementation of *ijārah* and IMBT as product financing at Bank BRI Syariah Yogyakarta Branch is carried out by banks to buy what customers want (such as houses and vehicles), then rent them out to their bank, at the end of the contract/agreement given by the bank to them, so that the leased goods are purchased by means of BRI Syariah (IMBT), or by handing them back to BRI sharia (*ijarah*). In practice, the operational basis is based on the National Sharia Council Fatwa No.09/DSNMUI/IV2003 Compilation of Economic and Sharia Law Chapter XI *Ijarah* and IMBT.

Sharia Marketing in Sharia Microfinance Institutions: Concept and Implementation at Puskopsyah D.I. Yogyakarta

According to Adinugraha, the structure of Islamic financial institutions is grouped into Islamic commercial banks, sharia BPRs and sharia cooperatives (*Bait al-Māl wa at-Tamwil*). These three institutions have different products and market shares. However, in terms of the principles and instruments used, the three Islamic financial institutions do not have a fairly basic difference, only in the scope of their activities. (Martono, 2002).

At the practical level, nowadays people have difficulty in distinguishing the principles and instruments of the LKS, between profit sharing, margin, and interest at conventional banks. Even if it is possible only at the theoretical level, empirically it still looks confusing. According to the theory of the profit sharing system with *mudharabah* and *musyarakah* contracts, it is very good, but this product has not been applied optimally in sharia-based cooperatives (call it BMT). So it can be said that BMT is the same as following the structure of conventional cooperatives or cooperatives that do not have "sharia" embellishments. (Adinugraha, 2017b).

Puskopsyah BMT DIY (originally named Puskopsyah BMT Mitra Nugraha) was established in order to achieve the ideals of national development which generally aims to create a just and prosperous society that is materially and spiritually evenly distributed. In terms of economic development and some conditions of development targets, Puskopsyah BMT DIY considers that all people need attention, especially for people whose lives are not adequate and are left behind.

Puskopsyah BMT DIY was initiated by the DIY Amil Zakat Infaq and Shodaqoh Agency (BAZIS) together with the Yogyakarta Muslim Charity Business Foundation (YAUMY) and the DIY Small Business Incubation Center (PINBUK) on April 1, 1997 under

the name BMT Mitra Nugraha (<http://puskopsyahjogja.blogspot.com/2009/10/background.html>).

From the results of Adinugraha's analysis, it shows that the application of the sharia marketing concept in Puskopsyah DIY is quite good, although not all aspects run perfectly. For example, the facts on the ground show that not all product marketing processes are carried out based on the prevailing fatwas which are supervised and issued by the Sharia Supervisory Board.

Closing

Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha is known as a lecturer at IAIN Pekalongan since 2019-present and also as a person who is productive in writing scientific papers. Several of his research works have been published in the form of articles, journals and books on the study of Islamic economics both on a national and international scale. His mindset continues to grow and continues to be productive in writing scientific papers to this day.

The concept and implementation of Islamic financial institutions according to Adinugraha, Islamic microfinance institutions (LKMS) are the same form as MFIs in general, the difference is the Islamic principles applied to products, contracts and operations. LKMS serves financing needs and facilitates a financing system for all micro-sectors. In the practice of Islamic economics, both banks and LKMS must avoid Magrib, an acronym for masyir, gharar and usury. (Adinugraha, 2017a).

Business development and community empowerment are carried out by providing loans or financing to people who have micro-scale businesses, managing savings, and providing business development consulting services that are not focused on profit. Because Islamic microfinance institutions offer more profitable services, they can be a solution for the poor, low-income people, or for owners of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs).

For example, in terms of savings, people can save or open deposits without having to go to the bank. Meanwhile, for loans and financing, the application requirements are easier and the financing period from daily to annual can be obtained if you apply at the LKMS. One LKMS facility that other financial institutions cannot provide is consulting services with experts in their fields who are not just looking for profit.

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